

PRELIMINARY CRUISE REPORT

Cruise name/number:	MoMARSAT 2023
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Authorizations:

Coastal State	Authorization Document Number	National Participant(s)
Portugal	NV86621/2023 AMP/2023/007 CCIR-RAA/2023/35 + Addenda	Daphne Cuvelier (IMAR, University of the Azores)

Scientist in charge of reporting:

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Brief description of scientific objective:

The MoMARSAT cruise series (<https://doi.org/10.18142/130>) ensures the annual maintenance of the EMSO-Azores observatory on the Lucky Strike vent field. This seabed observatory has been operating since 2010 and aims to acquire long time-series data (≥ 10 years) on hydrothermal, tectonic, volcanic processes and the associated ecosystems of an active hydrothermal field located on the Mid-Atlantic Ridge. EMSO-Azores is part of the European network EMSO ERIC (European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory - <http://emso.eu/>), supported in France by the Research Infrastructure (MESR) EMSO-FR whose management is ensured by a collaboration Ifremer-CNRS.

The array includes an observatory infrastructure that comprises a surface buoy (BOREL) ensuring the transfer of data by satellite to a server on land. Two junction boxes (SEAMON) deployed on the bottom communicate acoustically with BOREL and through a cable to the connected instruments. In its current configuration (after MOMARSAT 2023 maintenance), the "connected" part of the observatory includes a seismometer (OBS), a bottom pressure gauge, a biological observation module (TEMPO- with an HDTV camera and 2 projectors), an oxygen sensor and a turbidity sensor, an EMSO generic instrumentation module (EGIM) supporting an optode, a CTD, a hydrophone, a pressure gauge and an ADCP to measure Ocean Essential Variables, and four hydrophones (HYDROCTOPUS).

The infrastructure also includes autonomous instruments that store their data internally: 4 OBSs, 2 pressure sensors placed on the bottom, 34 autonomous temperature probes deployed within smokers and on diffusion zones, 5 autonomous current meters placed on the bottom, and 6 microbiological colonisers. These "unconnected" elements contribute to extend the spatial coverage of the area studied during each maintenance cruise.

Maintenance operations included the recovery of the BOREL buoy and oceanographic

mooring for upgrade, and the replacement of the two SEAMON infrastructure and the connected instruments after reconditioning on board. In situ sampling of rocks, fluids, fauna, microorganisms and the acquisition of imaging transects on targeted sites allow the multi-year monitoring of the system and complete the infrastructure data. These measurements are also used to calibrate/validate the measurements made by the instrumental array. Bottom operations were carried out by the Remotely Operated Vehicle VICTOR6000 onboard the Research Vessel L'Atalante. In order to optimize ship time, a physical oceanography program to study the plume dynamic over Lucky Strike was implemented in between dives. This year a big mapping effort was conducted to map geological and biological features at the vent field scale as well as scientific gear and dead weights. These maps will be shared with the Azoreans government to inform marine protected area management (PROTECT project).

The EMSO-Azores observatory is part of the One Ocean Network for Deep Observation action of Ifremer endorsed by the UN Ocean Decade program (<https://www.oceandecade.org/actions/one-ocean-network-for-deep-observation/>).

The MOMARSAT cruises and the infrastructure are supported and contribute to a number of project :

- EMSO ERIC (European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory, www.emso-eu.org/, DG J. Danobeitia)
- EU H2020 iAtlantic (Integrated assessment of the Atlantic Marine Ecosystems in space and time, <http://www.iatlantic.eu/>, coordinator M. Roberts University of Edinburgh, grant agreement No 818123). The MoMARSAT cruises contribute to WP1, WP2, WP3 and WP4 of the project. Repeated visits at Lucky Strike supported the acquisition of underwater imagery data and environmental measurements used for the spatio-temporal mapping of habitats and biological communities at the scale of the edifice and vent field (WP2, WP3). The data acquired by the observatory will contribute to the calibration of high resolution hydrodynamic models (WP1). This year a collaboration with Telmo Morato (Azores Univ.) and the Hydrographic Institute in Portugal will contribute to complete the high resolution mapping of the area as part of Seabed 2030.
- Abyssbox is a pressurised aquarium displaying live crabs and shrimps collected from the Lucky Strike hydrothermal field to the general public at the Oceanopolis aquarium in Brest (PI D. Barthélémy; Océanopolis). *Segonzacia mesatlantica* crabs and *Mirocaris fortunata* shrimp were collected, kept alive and shipped to Brest at Océanopolis for the general public exhibition "Abyssbox" started in 2012 in collaboration with Paris Sorbonne University (UPMC) and Ifremer.
- ANR IRONWOMAN: the collection of iron-rich microbial mats will feed the IRONWOMAN project (ANR-21-CE02-0012; PI C. Rommevaux 2021-2025). The project aims at validating the hypothesis of the primordial role of marine iron-oxidizing bacteria (FeOB) in promoting the development of iron-rich mats, and impacting the iron biogeochemical cycle and the primary production in the deep oceans, according to the variations in environmental conditions.
- DEEP REST: (PI J. Sarrazin – Ifremer- EU Biodiversa grant – 2022-2026) Conservation & restoration of deep-sea ecosystems in the context of deep-sea mining. DEEP REST will investigate two remarkable deep-sea ecosystems namely polymetallic nodule fields and hydrothermal vents, including their extended peripheries. Four major areas will be investigated: the Clarion Clipperton Zone (CCZ) and the DISCOL Experimental Area (DEA) in the Pacific Ocean for nodule fields and the northern Mid-Atlantic Ridge (nMAR), and the Arctic Mid-Ocean Ridge (AMOR) for active and inactive hydrothermal vents. These remote ecosystems are at risk of exploitation of their associated strategic metal resources, i.e. polymetallic nodules (PMN) and seafloor massive sulfides (SMS). However, questions about the impacts of mining and resilience

of deep sea communities to anthropogenic activities are still pending. DEEP REST will enhance fundamental knowledge on species and functional diversity and their interconnections to develop effective environmental management plans and regulations to protect unique and vulnerable marine habitats. We developed *in situ* experimental approaches to assess the effectiveness of passive restoration approaches on the recovery of ecosystem biodiversity, assess the response of fauna to hydrothermal sediment plume input and determine the growth rate of dominant species.

- Biological rhythms are a fundamental property of life. The circadian clock (~24-hour) is the only characterised biological clock to date, but it is not the only timekeeping system that nature provides. Marine ecosystems are shaped by environmental cycles, ranging from a few hours (tidal and solar cycles) to a year (seasons). And not only have biological rhythms been widely described in organisms, but they are also potentially present in all environments, including places where there is absolutely no solar light like deep-sea hydrothermal vents. Indeed, biological rhythms have recently been described in an hydrothermal mussel, *Bathymodiolus azoricus*, whose physiology and behaviour are under tidal influence at 1700 m depth. The project Audrey Mat is developing is a fundamental research project aiming at understanding the temporal functioning of the mussel *B. azoricus* and of its natural deep-sea environment. This includes working both at the behavioural and the molecular level to understand how *B. azoricus* timing system works and how it perceives its environment, synchronizes, and interacts with it. At the molecular level, she will use both genomics tools to get a big picture of the mussel, and target specific markers known for their role in the biological clock of shallow-water species. Audrey Mat initiated this work with us as a LabexMER postdoc. She recently joined the laboratory of Pr Kristin Tessmar-Raible, affiliated primarily with the University of Vienna in Austria, and also with the Alfred Wegener Institute in Germany. The work will be carried out in collaboration with Ifremer, and specifically Dr Marjolaine Matabos.
- Polymer degradation : we also started in 2022 a prospective deployment of material to study the degradation of biodegradable polymers in deep environment. 5 bags of samples were deployed in the vicinity of Seamon W in 2022 and the first bag was recovered this year. Collaboration P. Davies (Ifremer).
- ANR HotHg: fluid samples will be analysed to assess fluxes, speciation and transformation of mercury at hydrothermal vents. These analyses are conducted by Lars-Eric Heimbürger-Boavida at CNRS in Marseille, France.

The coordination of maintenance operations and the initial data exploitation are handled by Mathilde Cannat (EMSO France manager), Pierre Marie Sarradin (Azores node manager) and Marjolaine Matabos. The management of on-board operations is coordinated this year by Marjolaine Matabos and Laurent Gautier. The data acquired during the Momarsat cruises are available on the portal <http://www.emso-fr.org/fr/EMSO-Azores>. The study area is part of Portugal's EEZ and is also a "Marine Protected Area" (OSPAR).

Update on anticipated dates for delivery of final results:

Metadata:	6 month – Operational Cruise Report
Raw Data:	12 months
Processed Data:	24 months
Data Analysis:	2 to 5 years
WODC Data Registration (if applicable):	

Append image or URL illustrating the route of the platform, locations where measurements were taken, and actual cruise track:

Map of the Lucky Strike vent field and EMSO-Azores infrastructure

Map of the Multi-Beam Echosounder acquisition from Lucky Strike to Horta

Réf :
DRAFT STANDARD FORM C
Art 249 from UN Covention of law of the sea